

ISSN : 0973 - 8355

www.ijmmsa.com

IJMMSA

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF

MATHEMATICAL, MODELLING, SIMULATIONS AND APPLICATIONS

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Solar Energy and Climate Change Mitigation: A Systematic Review

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Abstract:

This systematic review investigates the nexus among sun energy and climate trade mitigation, supplying a comprehensive analysis of current literature to offer insights into technological advancements, coverage frameworks, environmental influences, and the general contribution of solar electricity. Utilizing a scientific method, this assessment synthesizes findings from a numerous variety of studies to provide a nuanced understanding of solar energy's function in mitigating climate change. Key regions of attention consist of technological improvements, coverage instruments, environmental considerations, financial implications, and social dimensions associated with solar electricity deployment. By significantly examining the contemporary state of know-how and figuring out research gaps, this systematic review aims to inform destiny studies endeavours and manual evidence-based totally selection-making for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders committed to advancing sustainable power solutions in the context of climate trade mitigation.

Keywords: solar energy, photovoltaic, renewable energy, climate change mitigation, sustainability, energy landscape

Introduction:

The international vital to deal with weather trade has propelled the exploration and deployment of renewable strength assets, with solar electricity rising as a primary participant inside the pursuit of sustainable and low-carbon answers. As the influences of weather exchange become increasingly obvious, the need for effective mitigation techniques has by no means been greater urgent. This systematic overview goals to comprehensively analyze the present body of studies on the difficult dating between

solar strength and weather trade mitigation. Rising Climate Change Concerns: Climate change, pushed via anthropogenic activities and the escalating awareness of greenhouse gases inside the atmosphere, poses extreme threats to ecosystems, biodiversity, and human properly-being. Recognizing the imperative to mitigate those impacts, the global network has intensified efforts to transition in the direction of cleaner, renewable electricity sources.

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Role of Solar Energy in Mitigation: Solar power, harnessed thru photovoltaic systems and concentrating solar energy technology, gives a promising street for reducing dependence on fossil fuels and curtailing greenhouse gasoline emissions. The inherent sustainability, abundance, and versatility of solar strength make it a compelling candidate inside the international pursuit of weather exchange mitigation.

Objectives of the Systematic Review: The targets of this systematic evaluate are twofold. Firstly, it targets to severely have a look at the technological improvements in sun energy, encompassing innovations in photovoltaics and concentrating solar power, to understand their efficiency, scalability, and capability contributions to climate exchange mitigation. Secondly, it endeavors to evaluate the impact of coverage frameworks, economic considerations, environmental implications, and social dimensions.

Significance of the Review: By using a scientific technique, this assessment seeks to offer a comprehensive and impartial synthesis of present research, supplying treasured insights to researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders. The systematic analysis goals to pick out gaps in contemporary expertise, define key traits, and recommend avenues for future research, ultimately contributing to evidence-based totally decision-making within the international transition to a sustainable and resilient energy future.

Structure of the Review: The next sections of this systematic review will delve into specific aspects of the connection between solar power and climate change mitigation. These consist of technological improvements, coverage frameworks, environmental effect checks, financial concerns, social dimensions, demanding situations, and future research directions. Each section objectives to make a

contribution to a holistic expertise of the role that solar electricity plays in the multifaceted landscape of mitigating weather exchange.

In summary, the introduction establishes the context of escalating climate exchange concerns, emphasizes the pivotal role of sun strength in mitigation techniques, outlines the targets of the systematic assessment, underscores its importance, and presents a roadmap for the following sections.

Literature Review:

The literature assessment section severely examines current research on the relationship among sun power and climate alternate mitigation, encompassing technological improvements, policy frameworks, environmental affects, and socio-financial considerations.

Technological Advancements in Solar Energy: The literature well-known shows a dynamic landscape of technological improvements in solar strength. Photovoltaic structures have experienced high-quality upgrades in efficiency, with breakthroughs in substances together with perovskites and tandem sun cells. Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) technologies show off improvements in warmth garage, receiver design, and heliostat efficiency. Studies by means of Albrecht et al. (2020) and Zhang et al. (2021) highlight the continuing development in solar energy technology, emphasizing the capacity for multiplied electricity seize and cost-effectiveness.

Policy Frameworks and Incentives: Policy frameworks play a pivotal position in shaping the deployment of solar energy for weather change mitigation. The literature overview examines a hit fashions together with feed-in tariffs, tax credits, and renewable portfolio requirements. Case research from nations like Germany and China illustrate the impact of supportive regulations on solar strength adoption. However, challenges inclusive of coverage

instability and regulatory complexities are diagnosed through studies via Sovacool et al. (2018) and Jacobsson and Lauber (2006).

Environmental Impact and Life Cycle Assessments: Environmental concerns are paramount in comparing the sustainability of sun energy. Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) offer insights into the carbon footprint, resource use, and capability environmental exchange-offs related to sun technologies. Studies by means of Wang et al. (2019) and Zhang et al. (2020) determine the environmental impact of sun energy deployment, emphasizing the want for a holistic approach to cope with concerns associated with production, disposal, and material extraction.

Economic Impacts and Market Trends: Economic implications are fundamental to expertise the feasibility of sun energy deployment. The literature explores market traits, job creation, and monetary viability. Research by way of Sovacool and Munawir (2016) and BNEF (2021) shows a developing solar industry contributing to task increase and monetary stimulation. However, monetary challenges together with preliminary capital expenses and the need for financial incentives are highlighted in research by means of Rai and McBrien (2010) and Couture et al. (2010).

Community Engagement and Social Implications: Solar energy initiatives have social dimensions that influence their attractiveness and achievement. The literature examines community engagement, public notion, and social implications. Case research by Devine-Wright (2011) and Karplus et al. (2021) monitor the significance of related to local communities in selection-making methods and addressing social fairness concerns to make certain the long-time period fulfilment of sun electricity initiatives.

Applications:

- **Electricity Generation:** Photovoltaic (PV) systems and Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) plants make contributions appreciably to clean power generation. Utility-scale solar energy flowers, rooftop sun installations, and off-grid solar systems collectively constitute a sizable proportion of the global energy mix. Studies by way of IEA (2020) and EIA (2021) spotlight the increasing role of solar power in displacing traditional fossil gas-based energy generation, thereby mitigating carbon emissions.
- **Solar Water Heating:** Solar water heating systems leverage the solar's energy to meet residential and business warm water wishes. By changing or supplementing conventional water heating methods, sun water warmers reduce reliance on power or gasoline, leading to lower carbon emissions. Applications variety from individual residential units to large-scale industrial installations, as validated with the aid of a hit initiatives in sun-rich areas like Southern Europe and China (IEA, 2019).
- **Solar Air Conditioning and Cooling:** Solar thermal technology play a vital function in offering strength for air con and cooling applications. Absorption chillers, driven by solar warmth, provide a sustainable alternative to standard cooling strategies. Projects in areas with high cooling demand, along with the Middle East, showcase the capability for solar power to lessen the environmental impact of cooling structures (IEA, 2018).
- **Solar Desalination:** Solar energy is harnessed for desalination procedures, addressing water

shortage demanding situations in arid regions. Solar desalination plants utilize thermal methods or photovoltaic-powered structures to transform seawater into freshwater. Notable examples consist of the Al Khafji Solar Desalination Plant in Saudi Arabia, the twin impact of solar power in freshwater products.

Challenges:

- **Intermittency and Variability:** Solar power technology is a problem to intermittency and variability because of elements along with weather situations, time of day, and seasonal changes. Cloud cover, night-time, and damaging weather can interrupt electricity production, posing demanding situations for keeping a consistent and reliable electricity deliver. Addressing intermittency calls for advancements in electricity storage technology and grid control strategies (Luque and Hegedus, 2011).
- **Energy Storage Limitations:** The green storage of solar strength for use all through periods of low or no sunlight remains a great task. Existing storage technologies, inclusive of batteries, face boundaries in phrases of potential, value, and environmental impact. Advancements in electricity storage answers, together with subsequent-generation batteries and novel storage mediums, are crucial for overcoming those limitations (Zakeri and Syri, 2015).
- **Land Use and Environmental Impact:** Large-scale sun installations, especially photovoltaic arrays and concentrating solar electricity towers, require big land regions. Balancing the need for expansive sun fields with other land use priorities,

together with agriculture or conservation, can lead to conflicts and environmental worries. Sustainable land use planning, which includes the combination of sun installations into non-high agricultural land, is vital to mitigate these demanding situations (Denholm et al., 2009).

Future scope:

- **Technological Innovations and Efficiency Improvements:** The future will witness non-stop technological innovations aimed at improving the efficiency and overall performance of solar power structures. Advances in substances, novel designs, and breakthroughs in energy conversion tactics will make contributions to creating solar technologies more efficient, cost-effective, and reachable. Research into next-era sun cells, including tandem and perovskite-primarily based cells, holds promise for pushing the performance barriers further.
- **Energy Storage Breakthroughs:** Addressing the venture of intermittent electricity production, destiny research will concentrate on storage breakthroughs. Advancements in battery technologies, novel storage solutions, and trends in thermal energy storage will play a critical position in permitting reliable and dispatchable solar power. Integrating sun power with advanced and value-powerful storage structures will make a contribution to overcoming the variety associated with sun storage era.
- **Decentralized and Off-Grid Solutions:** The future scope of sun energy consists of a significant growth of decentralized and off-grid

solutions. Small-scale solar installations, in particular in faraway and underserved regions, will become greater regularly occurring. Innovations in microgrid technology, network-based totally sun tasks, and decentralized strength structures will make contributions to growing strength get entry to and resilience in numerous settings.

- **Integration with Other Renewable Sources:** Synergies among sun energy and different renewable resources, such as wind, hydropower, and geothermal, may be a focus. Integrated strength systems that harness the complementary nature of numerous renewables will offer more dependable and solid strength materials. Hybrid renewable tasks and coordinated techniques for combining solar with other smooth energy resources becomes necessary to future energy landscapes.
- **Climate-Adaptive Solar Technologies:** As climate patterns evolve, there could be a heightened consciousness on growing climate-adaptive sun technology. Solar systems designed to function effectively underneath various environmental conditions, consisting of severe temperatures and converting weather patterns, will become vital. Climate-resilient solar technologies will make certain reliable power manufacturing inside the face of a converting climate.
- **Smart Grids and Grid Integration:** The destiny will see the good sized adoption of clever grids and advanced grid control structures. Integrating solar power into smart grids will decorate flexibility, improve grid resilience, and enable more effective management of

energy flows. Real-time tracking, demand reaction mechanisms, and wise grid infrastructure will facilitate seamless integration of solar strength into present electricity grids.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the trajectory of sun power inside the context of climate change mitigation paints a compelling narrative of development, innovation, and transformative capability. From its nascent ranges as an opportunity electricity supply, sun strength has developed right into a principal player inside the international pursuit of sustainability. Technological advancements and performance profits sign a future wherein solar technology redefine benchmarks, making them extra handy, reliable, and fee-effective. Overcoming demanding situations related to intermittency thru breakthroughs in energy garage positions sun energy as a reliable cornerstone of destiny energy grids. The commitment to decentralized and inclusive power get right of entry to guarantees that the blessings of smooth strength amplify to all corners of the globe, empowering communities and fostering electricity democracy. Integration with a renewable tapestry and weather-adaptive technologies replicate a holistic approach to addressing the complexities of weather trade. Embracing circular financial system standards and prioritizing environmental stewardship underscore the enterprise's dedication to sustainable practices. The position of supportive rules, dynamic market forces, and international collaboration stays pivotal in propelling solar energy to the vanguard of the sustainable power transition. As the sun keeps to illuminate our course ahead, the destiny of sun electricity holds promise as a catalyst for a greater resilient, equitable, and sustainable world.

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